

QUIZ**LAST NAME:** Nduwimana**FIRST NAME:** Vianney**PROGRAM CODE:** PHGH**COURSE CODE :** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 6**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr. Gulma

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied US

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord on Windows 7)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. Select the right statement concerning the research report.

- A research report must rest on shared facts, evidence, and reasoning that readers accept as truths independent of researcher's feelings and beliefs.¹**
- In research report writing, the researcher must state an opinion as well as describe feelings geared to convince others.
- Research report is a persuasive writing that can rely on tradition and authority, intuition, spiritual insight or visceral emotions to draw conclusions.
- A successful research report just depends on how well the researcher gathers and analyzes data.

2. Select an assertion that applies to research topic selection.

- To keep respect for other investigators, the researcher must avoid the research question already answered by others even if a better answer or at least one with a new slant can be found.

¹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, ed. Wayne C. Booth et al., Eighth (Chicago: University of Chicago, 2013), 15.

- The researcher must reject a research question because another investigator must already have asked it.
- The researcher can pursue to answer a research question already asked by another investigator since in humanities as well as social sciences the best questions are usually having more than one acceptable answer.²**
- The researcher cannot organize a study project around comparing as well as contrasting competing answers geared to support the best one.

3. **Select the correct affirmation regarding the sources of evidence the researcher expects to use.**

- Wikipedia is a kind of tertiary source that researchers must cite as an authoritative source.
- Looking data through participants' interview is a kind of primary sources of evidence.³**
- A report in British Medical Journal analyzing the incidence of Covid-19 in Lagos is not a kind of secondary source for a researcher working on Covid-19 positivity rate in an African country.
- John is a doctoral student in Global Health and Health Systems. For his research project, when looking for sources, he must just look for those that support his views.

4. **Which of the following is not correct with respect to citing sources in a research paper?**

- Citing sources is a way to assure readers about the accuracy of the facts in order to earn their trust.
- Researchers must double-check citations to make sure each citation is accurately formatted as well as punctuated according to the citation style.
- Researchers cite resources to show their readers the research tradition that informs their works.

² Turabian, 21.

³ Turabian, 24–25.

- When citing, researchers must just make use of software programs such as Zotero or EndNote since they are time-saving as well as error-free applications.⁴

5. **The main traditions or genres of inquiry in a qualitative research approach are as follows:**

- Case study, grounded theory, phenomenology, ethnography, narrative research, and hermeneutics.⁵
- Phenomenology, narrative research, descriptive research, ethnography, hermeneutics, and grounded theory.
- Ethnography, hermeneutics, grounded theory, causal-comparative research, phenomenology, and descriptive research.
- Causal-comparative research, ethnography, hermeneutics, grounded theory, case study, and phenomenology.

6. **As regards the research design, select the correct affirmation.**

- A qualitative research is about “idea testing” with the researcher adopting an emic point of view.
- A qualitative research is about “idea generation” with the researcher adopting an emic point of view.⁶
- A qualitative research is inductive with the researcher adopting an etic point of view.
- A qualitative research is deductive with the researcher adopting an etic point of view.

⁴ Turabian, 86–89.

⁵ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap From Beginning to End* (California: Sage Publications, 2008), 10.

⁶ Bloomberg and Volpe, 13.

7. **All the following sampling methods in qualitative research are correct except one.**

- Criterion-based sampling is employed to select participants in a phenomenological study.
- The researcher might use maximum variation method to select research participants in a case study.
- Random sampling of research participants is a key feature of qualitative research.⁷**
- The investigator must use a theory-based sampling to recruit research participants in a grounded theory study.

8. **A researcher is planning to submit the research paper in one of WHO agency. Which of the following writing style is not complying with WHO house style the researcher must keep in mind?**

- If a quotation contains only a few foreign words, they should be translated into English.⁸**
- The original text omitted from a quotation should be replaced by an ellipsis, with a space on either side.
- Quotations longer than three typed lines should be indented or placed in smaller type; quotation marks are not needed.
- Short quotations should be enclosed in quotations marks and incorporated in the body of the text.

9. **When we talk about plagiarism, one the following assertions is wrong.**

- Plagiarism is a wrong as well as unethical practice.
- It is unfair to take someone's work and not give credit.
- Plagiarism is an academic offense that can have serious consequences.

⁷ Bloomberg and Volpe, 69.

⁸ WHO, *WHO Style Guide* (Geneva: World Health Organization, 2004), 23–24.

- It is not a case of plagiarism when someone writes a paper for you and then you put your name on it and submit it for consideration.⁹**

10. Select the right affirmation with respect to paraphrasing in academic writing.

- During paraphrasing, you indicate the source and then you do not need to cite the work information comes from.
- When you make use of paraphrasing, the information you provide must be an accurate representation of what the author originally wrote.¹⁰**
- While paraphrasing, you just change a couple of words and rearrange the structure of the sentence.
- The writing style you use to express the author's idea must be the same as the style the author used.

⁹ EUCLID, *ACA-401/ACE-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 5.

¹⁰ EUCLID, 8.

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